

A Study of Institutional Satisfaction of the Students of Government Aided and Self-financed Colleges

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Student's satisfaction may be defined as an enjoyable and harmonious emotional state towards the facilities and services of the institutions / universities for their all – round development which is result of student's experience in the university.

As "Product specification is actually the minimum conditions for quality, but not the sufficient condition. The sufficient condition is customer satisfaction and beyond." (Mukhopadhyay, 2005) So, student's satisfaction is sufficient condition for quality in education. Student's satisfaction is understood as special form of customer satisfaction and comprised of five different categories i.e. curriculum, teachers, facilities, student's life and support (Kruger, 2009). Applying the consumer behaviour theory in education, we can regard students as consumer purchasing the services provided by institution. Therefore, the students have the right to obtain the best quality education (Clare, 2004). So, if a university / institution claim that their university / institution have quality in its education because of university / institution has excellent infrastructure, faculty, curriculum etc. is an insufficient base for their claim. If they assess student's satisfaction and if it is found to be very high then the university / institutions has quality in its education. It will also provide feedback as if the satisfaction found to be low, that can be rectified. So, constant assessment of student's satisfaction and use it as feedback to improve the status of education in the university / institution is the need for improvement.

As the competition and dynamism of educational environment are increasing regularly consequently the challenges are also increasing for the universities and Institutions. Now, students have several choices for their higher education. It becomes very important for the universities especially private universities and institutions identify the factors which attract and retain the students. It is prompting the universities and institutions to think about student's satisfaction.

As students are the direct recipient of the facilities and services of the institutions and the universities. If they are satisfied then their education can be take-up as quality education. So, the assessment of student's satisfaction is very important. It helps the administrations and policy makers to understand the strength and weaknesses of the facilities and services of the institutions / universities in order to improve the quality of education.

In the light of these observations, it was thought worthwhile undertake the research problem entitled: "**A Study of Institutional Satisfaction of the Students of Government Aided and Self Financed Colleges.**"

Definitions of the Terms

The definitions of the terms help to established the frame of references which the researcher approach. It also help to define variables in the operational terms. The definitions of the present study are as given below:

1. Student's Institutional Satisfaction

Though there is no universal definitions of satisfaction but it may be defined as an enjoyable, harmonious and emotional state towards the facilities and services of the institution/universities for their all round development which is result of students experience in the institution.

In the present study by institutional satisfaction means the aggregate scores obtained by the students on the five dimensions (i.e. – Tangibility, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance and Empathy).

2. Government Aided Colleges

In this study, the colleges located in Aligarh region that gets Aid or fund from the state / central government is termed as Government aided colleges.

3. Self Financed Colleges

In this study, the colleges located in Aligarh region that does not get any fund or Aid from the State/Central government are considered as self-financed colleges.

4. Students

In the present study, students means the boys and girls enrolled as a regular students of graduate and post-graduate classes in the colleges located in Aligarh region.

Assumptions of the Study

1. Students satisfaction contribute in the academic achievements of the students.
2. Students satisfaction play an important role in the all round development of the students.
3. Service quality is an important factor related to students satisfaction.
4. Students satisfaction closely associated with quality education.

Delimitations of the Study

Delimitations of the study are the boundaries of the study in respect to scope of the study and procedural treatment of the study.

1. The study will confine itself to the graduation and post-graduation level of students studying in Aligarh region (Aligarh, Etah, Kasganj and Hathras Districts)
2. The study will be confine only the comparison of the scores of students institutional satisfaction with the help of ‘t’ test.
3. The study will confine only the tool ‘student’s institutional satisfaction scale’ made by Dr. Sohrab Ali and Dr. Sanjeev Kumar Jha.
4. The study will confine only the variables students institutional satisfaction describe in the tool and the operational terms defined in the study.
5. The study will be confine to the survey method and the purposive method of sampling.

Objectives of the Study

Major Objectives :

1. To examine the relationship between the students of government aided and self financed colleges in concern the students institutional satisfaction.

Minor Objectives :

1. To find out the institutional satisfaction of **girls** students studying in government aided and self financed colleges.
2. To find out the institutional satisfaction of **boys** students studying in government aided and self financed colleges.
3. To find out the institutional satisfaction of **rural** students studying in government aided and self financed colleges.
4. To find out the institutional satisfaction of **urban** students studying in government aided and self financed colleges.

Hypotheses of the Study

To archive the objectives of the study researcher formulated the following hypotheses:

1. There will be no significant difference in relation to students satisfaction between the girls students of government aided and self-financed colleges.
2. There will be no significant difference in relation to students satisfaction in between the boys students of government aided and self financed colleges.
3. There will be no significant difference in relation to students satisfaction between the rural students of government aided and self financed colleges.
4. There will be no significant difference in relation to students satisfaction between urban students of government aided and self financed colleges.
5. There will be no significant difference in relation to students satisfaction between the students of self financed and government aided colleges in relation to institutional satisfaction.

Plan and Procedure of the Study

Descriptive research is used to describe characteristics of a population. Present study is a form of descriptive research which deals the distribution of phenomenon facts and events. In the descriptive research, survey method is most important technique to collect the data.

A survey is defined is a research method ued for collecting data from a pre-defined group of respondent to gain information and insights on various topic of interest. In the present study researcher used survey method to collect data related to students satisfaction with the help of students institutional scale made by S.S. Ali and S.K. Jha

Population of the Study

The population refers to any collection of specified group of human being or non-human identities. In our research project we deal mostly with finite population. In Aligarh region, total 19 government Aided colleges situated (in which 10 Aided and 9 government) and 174 colleges are self financed. These all colleges are affiliated to Dr. Bhim Rao Ambedkar University, Agra. The population of present study comprises in all the colleges as the students of graduation and post-graduation courses.

Sample of the Study

Researcher selected 250 students for the sample. The sample of 250 college going students selected with the help of purposive sampling technique in which 125 boys and 125 girls and 125 of rural students and 125 urban students respectively.

Table 1
List of Target Colleges and Selected Sample Units

S.No.	Colleges/ Institutions	Boys	Girls	Rural	Urban
1.	D.S. College, Aligarh	45	40	35	40
2.	Shri Varshney College, Aligarh	20	25	25	20
3.	I.I.M.T. Ramghat Road, Aligarh	20	20	25	20
4.	P.C. Bagla College, Hathras	20	20	20	15
5.	Nagar Palika P.G. College, Kasganj	20	20	20	20
	Total	125	125	125	125
		250		250	

Table 2
Target Sample According to Government Aided and Self Financed College

Colleges/ Institutions	Boys	Girls
Government Aided Colleges	65	65
Self Financed Colleges	60	60
Total	125	125

Table 3
Target Sample According to Government Aided and Self Financed College (Area Wise)

Colleges/ Institutions	Urban	Rural
Government Aided Colleges	70	60
Self Financed Colleges	55	65
Total	125	125

3.4 Tools of the Study

To fulfill the objectives of the study and collect the data, researcher used students ‘Institutional Satisfaction Scale’ developed by Dr. Sdrab Ali and Dr. Sanjeev Kumar Jha. In this test, SERVQUAL model by Parasramna Zaithmal and Berry, L.L. was adopted. This test measure the fine dimensions of students satisfaction :

1. Tengibility : Tengibility is the attribute of being easily detectable with the senses.
2. Reliability : The ability to be relied on or depended on as for accuracy-honesty or achievement.
3. Responsiveness : A quality of reacting quickly and positively.
4. Assurance : A promise that something will certainly happen or to be true.
5. Empathy : The ability to imagine how another person is feeling and so understand his/ her mood.

This tool is developed on the basis of likerts five points scale which has 47 items related to students satisfaction. It is highly reliable and valid test to measure students institutional satisfaction.

Procedure of Data Collection

Thus researcher contacted to the principals of the selected colleges and urges for the collection of data for the research. After the permission of principal, researcher went to the classes and form a rapport from the students and distributed the test papers with proper instructions. After the completion of the work, researcher collected the answer booklets from students. Researcher follow the same procedure upto the collection of decided data.

Analysis and Interpretation of the Data

The objectives of the present study is to find out the students institutional satisfaction and to make comparison in between government and self-financed colleges. To achieve the objectives, the researcher defines the population and target sample and then select a suitable tool to collect the data. After that, researcher will contact to the target colleges to collect the data. After collection and proper tabulation the following steps followed by the researcher to analysis data.

To achieve the objective of the study researcher made a strategic plan for the data analysis and discussion. The plan of the study is given under the following heads :

1. To study the relationship of institutional satisfaction of students studying government aided and self finance colleges.
2. To study the relationship of institutional satisfaction of girls students of government aided colleges.
3. To study the relationship of institutional satisfaction of the boys students studying in self finance and government aided colleges.
4. To study the relationship of institutional satisfaction of rural students studying in government aided and self finance colleges.
5. To study the relationship of institutional satisfaction of urban students studying in government aided and self finance colleges.

Institutional Satisfaction of Students Studying in Government Aided and Self Financed Colleges

In the present study, institutional satisfaction is treated as dependent variable. Gender (Boys and Girls) and locality urban and rural treated as independent variable. After tabulation of data researcher calculated mean and standard deviation of institutional satisfaction in regarding to four independent variable (Boys, Girls, Rural and Urban). The mean and standard deviation of the institutional satisfaction is given below :

Table 4
Institutional Satisfaction of Girls Students

Type of Colleges	N	Mean	SD	't' value
Government Aided Colleges	65	160	10.30	t = 1.38
Self Financed Colleges	60	163	13.70	
Total	125			

Table 5
Institutional Satisfaction of Boys Students

Type of Colleges	N	Mean	SD	't' value
Government Aided Colleges	65	164	11.30	t = 1.06
Self Financed Colleges	60	166	9.80	
Total	125			

Table 6
Institutional Satisfaction of Rural Students

Type of Colleges	N	Mean	SD	't' value
Government Aided Colleges	60	167	13.60	t = 0.85
Self Financed Colleges	65	169	11.98	
Total	125			

Table 7
Institutional Satisfaction of Urban Students

Type of Colleges	N	Mean	SD	't' value
Government Aided Colleges	70	165	10.89	t = 0.46
Self Financed Colleges	55	166	12.60	
Total	125			

Table 8
Institutional Satisfaction of Students

Type of Colleges	N	Mean	SD	't' value
Government Aided Colleges	125	163	10.52	t = 2.32
Self Financed Colleges	125	166	11.02	
Total	250			

Objective 1 : Objective 1 of the present study is related to find out the **institutional satisfaction of the girls students** of self financed colleges and government aided colleges.

After the calculation of mean and standard deviation researcher calculate Z score to explain the row score. The Z score are as given below :

Table 9
Institutional Satisfaction of Girls Students

Type of Colleges	N	Mean	Z-Score	S.D.
Government Aided Colleges	60	160	- 0.25	10.30
Self Financed Colleges	65	163	-0.13	13.70

The above table indicates that the Z-score of girls students institutional satisfaction are -0.25 and -0.13. The manual of SISS table of Norms interpretation express that -0.50 to +0.50 Z-score of grade D express Average / moderate level of satisfaction. After that researcher calculated the ‘t’ value of the scores to find out the significant difference in between the scores of girls studying in government aided and self financed colleges the ‘t’ value is as given below :

Table 10
Significant difference of the Scores (Girls)

Type of Colleges	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value
Government Aided Colleges	60	160	10.30	t = 1.38
Self Financed Colleges	65	163	13.70	

The ‘t’ value of the scores of the girls students of government colleges and self financed colleges was found 1.38. This value of ‘t’ is less than the referred value on .01 level (2.57) and .05 level (1.98) so the null hypothesis No. 1 is accepted on .05 level. It indicate that there is no significant difference in the scores of girls students of government aided colleges and self financed colleges.

Objective 2 of the present study is related to find out the **institutional satisfaction of the Boys students** of government aided and self financed colleges. After the calculation of mean and standard deviation, researcher calculated the Z-score, to explain the raw scores. The Z scores are as given below:

Table 11
Institutional Satisfaction of Boys Students

Type of Colleges	N	Mean	Z-Score	S.D.
Government Aided Colleges	65	164	- 0.09	11.30
Self Financed Colleges	60	166	± 0.00	9.80

The above table indicates that the Z-score of Boys students institutional satisfaction are -0.09 and ± 0.00. The manual of SISS Table of Norms interpretation shows that -0.50 to + 0.50, Z score of grade D express Average / moderate level of satisfaction. After that researcher calculated ‘t’ value of the scores to find out the significant difference in between the scores of Boys studying in government aided and self financed colleges. The ‘t’ values is as given below :

Table 12
Significant difference of the Scores (Boys)

Type of Colleges	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value
Government Aided Colleges	65	164	11.30	t = 1.06
Self Financed Colleges	60	166	9.80	

The ‘t’ value of the scores of the boys students of government aided colleges and self financed colleges was found 1.06, this value of ‘t’ is less than the referred value on .01 level (2.57) and .06 level (1.98). So the null hypothesis number 2 is accepted on .05 level, it indicate that there is no significant difference in between the scores of boys students studying in government and self financed colleges.

Objective 3 of the present study is related to find out the **institutional satisfaction of the rural students** studying in government aided and self financed colleges. After the calculation of mean and standard deviation, researcher calculated Z score, to explain the raw score. The ‘z’ score are as given below:

Table 13
Institutional Satisfaction of Rural Students

Type of Colleges	N	Mean	Z-Score	S.D.
Government Aided Colleges	60	167	+0.03	13.60
Self Financed Colleges	65	169	+0.11	11.98

The above table indicates that the Z-score of Rural students. Institutional satisfaction are +0.03 and +0.11. The manual of SISS table of Norms interpretation show that -0.50 to +0.50, Z score of grade D. Average / moderate level of satisfaction. After that, researcher calculated ‘t’ value of the scores to find out the significant difference in between the scores of rural students studying in government aided and self financed colleges. The ‘t’ value is as given below:

Table 14
Significant difference of the Scores (Rural)

Type of Colleges	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value
Government Aided Colleges	60	167	13.60	t = 0.85
Self Financed Colleges	65	169	11.98	

The ‘t’ value of the scores of the students of government aided colleges and self financed colleges was found 0.85. The value of ‘t’ is less than the referred value as .01 level (2.57) and on 0.05 level (1.98). So the null hypothesis number 3 is accepted and .05 level. It indicates that there is no significant difference in between the scores of Rural students studying in government aided and self financed colleges.

Objective 4 of the present study is related to find out the **institutional satisfaction of the urban students** of government aided and self financed colleges. After the calculation of the mean and standard deviation, researcher calculated the Z-scores to explain raw scores. The Z-score are as given below:

Table 15
Institutional Satisfaction of Urban Students

Type of Colleges	N	Mean	Z-Score	S.D.
Government Aided Colleges	70	165	-0.05	10.89
Self Financed Colleges	65	166	±0.00	12.60

The above table indicates that the Z-score of Urban students, Institutional satisfaction are - 0.05 and ±0.00. The manual of SISS table of Norms interpretation show that -0.50 to +0.50, Z score of grade D indicate Average / moderate level of satisfaction. After that, researcher calculated ‘t’ value of the scores to find out the significant difference in between

the scores of urban students studying in government aided and self financed colleges. The ‘t’ value is as given below:

Table 16
Significant difference of the Scores (Urban)

Type of Colleges	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value
Government Aided Colleges	70	165	10.89	t = 0.46
Self Financed Colleges	55	166	12.60	

The ‘t’ value of the scores of the urban students studying in government aided colleges and self financed colleges was found 0.46. The value of ‘t’ is less than the referred value as .01 level (2.57) and on 0.05 level (1.98). So the null hypothesis number 4 is accepted and .05 level. It indicates that there is no significant difference in between the scores of Urban students studying in government aided and self financed colleges.

Objective 5 of the present study was related to find out the students **institutional satisfaction of the students** studying in government aided and self financed colleges. After the calculation of the mean and standard deviation, researcher calculated Z-score to explain the raw scores. The Z-score are as given below:

Table 17
Students Institutional Satisfaction

Type of Colleges	N	Mean	Z-Score	S.D.
Government Aided Colleges	125	163	-0.13	10.52
Self Financed Colleges	125	166	±0.00	11.02

The above table indicates that the Z-score of the students studying in government colleges is 0.13 and for self financed colleges is ± 0.00. The manual of SISS Table of Norms Interpretation shows that -0.50 to +0.50. Z-score of grade D indicate Average / Moderate level of satisfaction. After that, researcher calculated ‘t’ value of the scores to find out the significant difference in between the scores of students studying in government aided colleges and self financed colleges. The ‘t’ value is as given below:

Table 18
Significant difference of the Scores of the Students (Overall)

Type of Colleges	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value
Government Aided Colleges	125	163	10.52	2.32
Self Financed Colleges	125	166	11.02	

The ‘t’ value of the scores of the students studying in government aided and self financed colleges was found 2.32. This value is less than the value on .01 level 2.57 and more than the value 1.98 on .05 level. So the null hypothesis no. 5 accepted on .05 level of significant and rejected on .01 level. It indicate the difference on .01 level regarding to institutional satisfaction after students studying in government aided and self financed colleges.

Conclusion, Discussion and Implication

The objective of the present study was to find out the institutional satisfaction of the students studying in government aided and self financed colleges of Aligarh. To achieve the

objectives, researcher formulate the null hypothesis regarding to the various independent variable e.g. Gender and location.

Findings of the Study

On the basis of analysis of the data researcher find the following facts:

1. The mean score of the institutional satisfaction of girls students studying in government aided and self financed colleges is found 160 and 163 simultaneously and 't' value found 1.38 that is non significant on .05 level. So the hypothesis no. 1 is accepted on 0.05 level.
2. The mean score institutional satisfaction of Boy students studying in government and Self financed colleges found 160 and 163 simultaneously and 't' value found 1.06 that is non significant on .05 level. So the hypothesis no. 2 is accepted on .05 level.
3. The mean score of institutional satisfaction of Rural students studying in Government aided and self finance colleges found 167 and 169 simultaneously and 't' value found .85 that is non significant on .05 level. So the hypothesis no. 3 is accepted on .05 level.
4. The mean score of institutional satisfaction of urban students studying in government aided and self finance colleges found 165 and 166 simultaneously. And 't' value found .046 that is non significant on .05 level. So the hypothesis no. 4 is accepted on .05 level.
5. The overall mean score of the institutional satisfaction of the students studying in government and self financed colleges found 103 and 166 simultaneously and 't' score found 2.23 that is significant on .05 level and non significant on .01 level of confidence. So the hypothesis no. 5 is accepted on .05 level.

Conclusions of the Study

Research is a objective centered process that draw conclusions about the statement of the problem. The present study is an attempt to find out the institutional satisfaction of the students studying in the government aided and self financed colleges. After the calculation of the data researcher draw some findings and as a final statement of the following conclusion made by the researcher:

1. The institutional satisfaction of the boys students found average / moderate level. There is no significant difference in the boys of government aided and self financed colleges. But the boys of self financed college expresses above average satisfaction then the boys of government aided colleges.
2. The institutional satisfaction of the girls students found Average / moderate level. There is no significant difference found of girls government aided and self financed colleges. But the girls of self financed colleges express above average institutional satisfaction than the girls of government aided colleges.
3. The institutional satisfaction of the rural students found average / moderate level. There is no significant difference found of Rural students of self financed and government aided colleges. But the rural students of self financed express above average institutional satisfaction than the government aided colleges.
4. The institutional satisfaction of the urban students found average / moderate level. There is no significant difference found of the urban students of government aided and self financed colleges but the urban students of self financed colleges express above average satisfaction than the government aided colleges.
5. The institutional satisfaction of the total students found average / moderate level. There is no significant difference found on institutional satisfaction in between the students of self financed colleges and government aided colleges on .05 level of confidence but on .01 level is significant difference found. It express that there is some difference is actual exist between the students of both type of schools.

Educational Implication of the Study

The objective of the present study was to find out the institutional satisfaction of the students studying in the government aided and self financed college of the Aligarh. The findings express that the level of institutional satisfaction of the students is average / moderate level and the students of self financed college study express higher satisfaction comprehensive to the students of government aided colleges. The implementation of the results of present study explained in the following points:

1. Institutional satisfaction of the students is directly associated with the quality of education so the measurement of satisfaction also express the quality of education.
2. The institutional satisfaction indicate the efficiency of organizational climate of the college so the average level of college climate need to important.
3. Students satisfaction of self finance colleges is higher so it is a indication to the government colleges to improve their academic climate.
4. The institutional satisfaction also helpful to find out the condition of internal discipline of the institution so if we try to improve the institutional satisfaction the problem of indiscipline automatically solved.
5. Institutional satisfaction is a feeling of students towards the institution so it is a matter of achievement of the students and growth of institution.

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